
Advertisement of Job Vacancies and Service Delivery in the Nigeria Public Sector: A Study of Selected Ministries, Departments in Anambra State (2013-2024)

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Abstract

This study examined the relationship between advertisement of job vacancies and service delivery in selected ministries and departments in Anambra State. Whereas the public sector in Nigeria is expected to render effective service in the vital role of implementing policies and programmes of governments, there have been concerns over the effectiveness of the sector in Anambra state and the role of advertisement of job vacancies in attracting competent employees for effective service delivery. This, therefore, necessitated this study which sought to determine the nexus between advertisement of job vacancies and service delivery in the selected ministries and departments in the state from 2013 to 2024. The study adopted Resource-Based View Theory as the framework of analysis. Survey research design was utilised to collate relevant data from primary sources through the use of structured questionnaire. Test of hypothesis was carried out at 0.05 level of significance using Chi-Square (χ^2). Among other things, the study revealed that the failure to give wide publicity to all vacant positions and transparently conduct all stages of the recruitment did not encourage effective service delivery in the selected ministries and departments within the period reviewed. It, therefore, recommended appropriate legislation criminalising employment into government ministries and departments in the state without evidence of sustained publicity of the job vacancies.

Keywords: Advertisement of job vacancies, service delivery, effectiveness, Nigerian public sector, Anambra state

1.0 Introduction

Public service serves as catalyst for development in any country. This explains why quality of personnel recruited into the service for the performance of public functions is essential (Onwe, Abah & Nwokwu, 2016; Ndukwe et al, 2023).

Successive governments in Nigeria had made efforts to improve on service delivery in government functions, particularly the civil service through various reform programmes. However, the sector seems to have remained inefficient as a result of perceived poor recruitment process adopted over time that could not result ineffective service delivery (Chukwuemeka, Okeke & Onwuchekwa, 2018; Dike & Onyekwelu, 2018; Kings, 2018; Ndukwe et al, 2023). Recruitment into Anambra state civil service, in particular, appears not to have been undertaken methodically to attract competent personnel. The recruitment process into the state civil service appears to have skipped important stages like advertisement of job vacancies. There is suspicion that successive administrations in the state carried out recruitments into the nineteen (19) ministries, eleven (11) non-ministerial departments without sustained advertisement of vacant job positions (Adeoye, 2021). The perceived poor quality service delivery has, consequently, become worrisome and often linked to this practice of secret recruitments (Ogu & Chukwurah, 2023; Salawudeen, 2017; Idigo, 2023). It is on the basis of these concerns that this study was conceived to examine the relationship between advertisement of job vacancies and service delivery in selected ministries and departments in Anambra State, more so as scanty scholarly literature has interrogated this concern.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Advertisement of Job Vacancies as Crucial Recruitment Process

Public sector organisations develop and implement strategies that enable them optimise their recruitment goals since decisions made during recruitments can have far-reaching impact on service delivery (Oboh, et al, 2021). In recognition of this fact, recruitment into the public sector in Nigeria, particularly the civil service is specifically guided by the principles of openness, such that qualified applicants are given equal opportunity based on merit. Recruitment process, generally, involves advertisement of job vacancies undertaken in order to increase the likelihood of hiring individuals who possess the right skills and abilities to be successful at their jobs (Oyadiran et al, 2023). Thus, the technique of locating job applicants who are qualified for jobs begins with publicizing current vacancies ((Armstrong, 2016; Cooper & Sheena, cited in Oyadiran et al, 2023).

Recruitment into public service entails advertisement of vacant jobs through various channels, inviting applications (Gilbert & Ndubuisi, 2023). Since the fundamental reason behind recruitment is to attract eligible candidates and employing the right process to fill up the range of vacant positions, recruitment process, therefore, involves sourcing for candidates through advertising. It has been argued that proper advertisement amasses an expansive pool of qualified candidates for employers. Thus, there is need for advertisement of available jobs in different media outlets such as newspapers, websites, and social media (Madia, 2011). Depending on the circumstances of the unoccupied positions and the organization's policies, recruitment can be done either domestically or outside while the acquisition might also assume advertising shape of a direct mail, use of employment agencies, career fairs, as well as use of traditional media and the internet. At the end, all submissions received within recruitment deadline are reviewed and those who do not satisfy the advertising criteria are instantaneously disregarded (Torlak et al., 2018). Generally, it has often been contended that a faulty and inefficient recruitment process leads to a high rate of frustration, absenteeism, and

other several conditions which have far-reaching negative consequences for service delivery (Anazodo et al., 2012).

Certain challenges trouble recruitment into public service in Nigeria and these include lack of independence of the recruitment bodies as well as commercialisation of appointments and infusion of sentiments. In practice, the recruiting commissions are oftentimes influenced and pressured by the different arms of government, friends, family members and others who are regarded to be powerful in the country to the extent that the pressures and influences from the interested parties affect the independence of the commissions and dissuade suitable candidates from competing for appointments. The pressures and influences also affect the principles of merit and equal opportunities (Madugu & Okafor, 2015).

2..1.1 History and Factors Affecting Service Delivery in the Public Sector

Historically, Nigerian public service began as an instrument of occupation designed to facilitate colonial rule and the exploitation of Nigeria and its people for the benefit of the colonial masters. Notably, exploitation was at the heart of colonialism (Okeke, 2018). Nevertheless, in 1936, the Walayns Committee recommended a new policy of staffing the public service by indigenes and for the first time the administrative service which was the cream of colonial services was thrown open to Nigerians. The Nigerianisation scheme went a stage further with the appointment of the Foot Commission of 1948 which observed that the training and recruitment of Nigerians for senior post in the government services was not only necessary to enable Nigerians to take part in the management of their own affairs but also required to enable them keep pace with the constitutional development and programmes in the country (Ciroma, cited in Salawudeen, 2017; Yusuf, 2013).

There is a consensus that the Richard Constitution of 1946 marked a significant milestone in the history of public service in Nigeria. First, it marked the beginning of the regionalization of the hitherto unitary public service with attempts to regionalize the central department. Second, the regionalization of the public service introduced by the constitution took the form of transforming some of the central departments operating in the three regions into non-central departments headed by deputy directors responsible to the director in Lagos. Be that as it may, Salawudeen (2017) noted that Macpherson constitution of 1951 further extended the regionalization policy as more Central Departments were regionalized. According to him, the 1954 constitution provided for a full-fledged regional public service as well as the central (federal) civil service, and brought in many structural changes which were of great significance in the Public Service Commission in the regions as well as at the center with full powers granted by the same constitution to the commission to appoint, promote, dismiss and discipline junior civil servants.

Public service in Nigeria has been plagued by several challenges. It is in recognition of the poor service delivery of the public service that Olusegun Obasanjo administration's Service Delivery Reform of 2003 was instituted (Okeke, 2020). As Ajayi (cited in Dominic & Peter, 2021) noted, key factor affecting service delivery in Nigeria public service remains poor recruitment procedures. This implies all the practices that bypass the application of the necessary recruitment processes that include advertisement of vacant job positions. It includes all the sharp practices where jobs are reserved for those who have the economic power to pay at the expense of those who have the expertise. Rather than methodically apply all the recruitment processes, applicants often desperately search for influential contacts to secure jobs for them into public service. When this happens, the recruiting commissions and other delegated recruiting authorities come under pressure to recruit unqualified persons. In essence, sentiments of tribalism, nepotism, religion, sectionalism/regionalism, clanism,

among others are brought to bear in recruitments into Nigerian public service (Madugu & Okafor, 2015).

2.1.2 Service Delivery in Anambra State Public Service

There is a belief that public service in Anambra state is not immune from the challenges troubling the service in the rest of the country. Anambra State civil service in particular is, in fact, characterized by low morale in the sense that punctuality and dedication to work is no longer the priding administrative attitude of the service. The situation is such that there are hurdles or challenges in managing the service of the civil servants in the state (Nwobi et al., 2021). As Nwakoby et al (2021) put it, service delivery in Anambra state civil service was very poor in all ramifications such that the performance output of employees was of prime concern to the public.

Over the years, service delivery in Anambra state public service has slackened such that it indicates poor service delivery, records poor performance, and is largely seen as maintaining the legacy and poor productivity orientation bequeathed by the colonial era (Nwakoby et al., 2021). The inefficiency in service delivery could be attributed to several reasons. For instance, recruitment process is more or less affiliated to networking and political inclinations as against the notion that organizations select people with the quality essential for continued success in the workplace through proper recruitment and selection practices. Unfortunately, the processes of recruitment are often characterised by favouritism and god-fatherism in which case the employees' loyalty will only be to the god-fathers and not to the service and this adversely affects organizational effectiveness (Chukwuemeka et al, 2018).

2.2 Theoretical Framework

Resource-Based View Theory was adopted in this study as the framework of analysis. Propounded by Jay Barney in 1991, the theory contends that the calibre of people employed and the quality of their work and relationships account for most of the organisation's successes or failures (Barney, 1991). It recognises human resource as the most crucial among all the resources available in an organisation through the pool of highly qualified and motivated employees, and insists that even though all resources are essential for any given organisation to achieve her objectives sustainably, human capital remains the most valuable. According to the resource-based view theory, recruitment processes that are effective lead to desired organisational outcomes. Thus, the theory explains that all organisations that have achieved exceptional competence have done so because of their remarkable and non-substitutable human resources (Cayago, 2023).

The Resource-Based Theory very well fits into the objective of this study and valuable in examining the relationship between advertisement of job vacancies and service delivery in the selected ministries and departments in Anambra State. The core gist of the theory underscores the importance of advertisement of job vacancies to attract the right or competent employees who will drive the objectives of public service in the state to actuality. It is a theory that guides the study and forms its bedrock in appraisal of this core relation between the variables of the study.

2.2.2 Empirical Review

Previous studies had attempted to examine factors affecting service delivery in Anambra state public service. For instance, Ogu and Chukwurah (2023) investigated "E-governance and Public Service delivery in Nigeria: A study of Anambra State Civil Service: 2018-2022" using survey research design and 6,955 employees in Anambra State Civil Service, out of which a sample size of 361 staff were drawn using Krejcie and Morgan's sample size

determination table. Finding is that the application of e-governance has positively affected public service delivery in Anambra State Civil Service.

Equally, in their paper titled, “Impact of Effective Employee Performance Management on Organizational Productivity: A Study of Anambra State Civil Service System, Nigeria”, Mgbemena, Mbah and Ejike (2015) using a survey design found that transparent performance appraisal process affects employee performance positively and significantly. It also found out that cordial labour-management relations enhance organizational productivity significantly, and that selective disciplinary measures administration in an organization is a drawback on employee’s performance.

Obiora (2012) conducted a study titled “Wages Administration and Civil Service Productivity in Anambra State: An Empirical Analysis”. The study examined how wages administration in Anambra State Civil Service impacts on staff productivity. The study adopted the survey research method to collect data which were analysed based on simple percentage and chi-square (χ^2). The study found out that while the wages and salaries of civil servants are their rights and entitlements, the manner by which they are determined and paid in the state civil service leaves much to be desired as it has enormous influence on staff morale and productivity. Consequently, the study recommended that at intervals, the state government should review the wages and salaries of civil servants so as to ensure that it reflects the economic realities of the period it is being paid.

Orakwe (2021) in a study titled “Compensation Packages and Civil Servants’ Performance in State Ministries in Anambra State”, investigated compensation packages and civil-servants performance in state ministries in Anambra state. The specific objectives of the study were to examine the effect of competency-based compensation, merit-based compensation, job-based compensation, performance-based compensation and skills-based compensation on employee performance. The study was anchored on Equity Theory while descriptive research survey was adopted. The population of the study comprised 1423 selected civil servants in state ministries in Anambra State, Nigeria, while the sample size consists of 302 civil servants. Krejcie and Morgan sampling formula was used to obtain the sample size. Face and content validity method was used to ensure validity of the instrument, and the reliability of the instrument was achieved through test re-test method. Simple percentage analysis was employed to answer the research questions, as Pearson Product Correlation Method analysis was conducted to assess the relative predictive power of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The study found that there is a strong and significant positive relationship between competence-based, merit-based, and job-based compensation on employees’ performance. The study recommended among others that every organization should formulate competency-based compensation policy for increased employee productivity.

Nweke and Chukwuemeka (2020) examined “The effect of capacity building on employees’ service delivery: A study of Anambra state Civil Service Commission (2015 – 2019)”. The study employed survey design; where questionnaire was used to collect data. The collated data were analyzed using weighted mean and descriptive statistics while the inferential statistics such as Regression analysis with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20 was used to analyze the hypotheses. The study used Capital Development Theory as its theoretical frame work and found that poor training and re-training of employees affect service delivery, while effective funding of capacity building programmes promote service delivery in Anambra State Civil Service Commission. It therefore recommended that training of employees based on favouritism should be discouraged by the management, and also a mechanism should be created for proper assessment and evaluation

of employee performance after training. It also recommended that the Human Resources department should ensure that adequate training design that is rich in content is used for employee training.

In his study titled, “Staff Recruitment and Selection as a Means of Enhancing Productivity in the Local Government (A case study Of Ihiala Local Government Area of Anambra State)”, Ihama, B. (2018), examined the relevance of recruitment and selection process to achieve the goals of an organization, taking Ihiala Local Government Area of Anambra State, as case study. The research design used was both case study and survey design. Simple percentages were used to analyze the research questions posed. The major finding of the study was that recruitment and selection were not given a serious thought as unqualified people were engaged. To that effect, the study recommended that competent and qualified workforce should be selected after recruitment exercise to guarantee effectiveness and efficiency in Ihiala Local Government Area of Anambra State.

2.2.2.1 Summary of Literature Review

The review of related literature on service delivery in the public sector in Anambra state revealed some gaps. For instance, the review of literature showed that previous scholars focused generally on recruitment and employees’ performance in the public service without particular attention paid to advertisement of job vacancies and its relationship with service delivery in Anambra public sector. That was a major gap. Also, previous attention focused generally on civil service in Anambra state without selecting specific ministries and departments for an in-depth study. Such generic study of the whole civil service in the state was a deficiency noticed in previous studies which was addressed in this study that narrowed its investigation down to selected ministries and departments. More so, it was revealed that previous studies on the subject matter have become obsolete. This study, therefore, becomes one of the current literatures on the subject matter. The survey design adopted in the study was also an advantage that contributed to the empirical value of the research.

3.0 Methodology

3.1 Research Design

Survey research design was employed in this study. The choice of this design was to extract relevant data from primary sources that are knowledgeable in the subject of investigation. Using the questionnaire instrument, the study reached out to employees in the selected ministries and departments in order to establish the influence of recruitment test on technical competence of employees in selected ministries and departments in Anambra state and did not need to rely on secondary sources (documents). This informed the choice of survey design for the study.

3.2 Population of the Study

The population of the study is 2,414. This is made up of all the staff members of the nine ministries and two non-ministerial departments examined in this study. The population distribution is presented on Table 3.1.

Table 3.1 Population Distribution

S/NO	MINISTRY/NON-MINISTERIAL DEPARTMENT	POPULATION	PERCENTAGE
1	Civil Service Commission	80	3
2	Office of Head of Service	251	10
3	Ministry of Finance	468	20
4	Ministry of Youth Development	188	8
5	Ministry of Information	73	3
6	Ministry of Health	276	11
7	Ministry of Agriculture	405	17
8	Ministry of Homeland Affairs	65	3
9	Ministry of Works	213	9
10	Ministry of Lands	321	13
11	Ministry of Budget and Economic Planning	74	3
	Total	2,414	100

Source: Office of Head of Service (2025)

3.3 Sample Size Determination

Taro Yamane (1964) sample size determination formula was adopted in determining the sample size of the study. It is rendered mathematically as:

$$S = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where S = Sample size
 1 = Constant
 N = Population size
 E = Margin of error, usually 5% (0.05)

$$S = \frac{2,414}{1 + 2,414 (0.0025)}$$

$$S = \frac{2,414}{1 + 6.04}$$

$$S = \frac{2,414}{7.04}$$

$$S = 343$$

After determining the sample size of the study, Bowley Sample Technique was used to decide the sample size for each stratum as below:

Civil Service Commission

$$\frac{80 \times 343}{2,414} = \frac{27,440}{2,414} = 11.36 = 11$$

Head of Service

$$\frac{251 \times 343}{2,414} = \frac{86,093}{2,414} = 35.66 = 36$$

Ministry of Finance

$$\frac{468 \times 343}{2,414} = \frac{160,524}{2,414} = 66.49 = 66$$

Ministry of Youth Development

$$\frac{188 \times 343}{2,414} = \frac{64,484}{2,414} = 26.71 = 27$$

Ministry of Information

$$\frac{73 \times 343}{2,414} = \frac{25,039}{2,414} = 10.37 = 10$$

Ministry of Health

$$\frac{276 \times 343}{2,414} = \frac{94,668}{2,414} = 39.21 = 39$$

Ministry of Agriculture

$$\frac{405 \times 343}{2,414} = \frac{138,915}{2,414} = 57.54 = 58$$

Ministry of Homeland Affairs

$$\frac{65 \times 343}{2,414} = \frac{22,295}{2,414} = 9.23 = 9$$

Ministry of Works

$$\frac{213 \times 343}{2,414} = \frac{73,059}{2,414} = 30.26 = 30$$

Ministry of Lands

$$\frac{321 \times 343}{2,414} = \frac{110,103}{2,414} = 45.61 = 46$$

Ministry of Planning and Economic Development

$$\frac{74 \times 343}{2,414} = \frac{25,382}{2,414} = 10.51 = 11$$

Total = 343

Table 3.2: Sample Size Distribution

S/NO	MINISTRY/NON-MINISTERIAL DEPARTMENT	POPULATION	SAMPLE SIZE	PERCENTAGE
1	Civil Service Commission	80	11	3
2	Office of Head of Service	251	36	10
3	Ministry of Finance	468	66	20
4	Ministry of Youth Development	188	27	8
5	Ministry of Information	73	10	3
6	Ministry of Health	276	39	11
7	Ministry of Agriculture	405	58	17
8	Ministry of Homeland Affairs	65	9	3
9	Ministry of Works	213	30	9
10	Ministry of Lands	321	46	13
11	Ministry of Budget and Economic Planning	74	11	3
	Total	2,414	343	100

Source: Research Report, 2025

3.4 Sampling Technique

Random sampling technique was adopted in selecting employees of the ministries and non-ministerial departments who served as respondents. The choice of this technique was to eliminate bias in selecting respondents who may, in turn, be biased in their responses.

3.5 Instrument of Data Collection

Structured questionnaire instrument was adopted for data collection from primary sources. It has two sections. Section A contained the bio-data of the respondents while Section B contained the metric questions consisting of six questions designed to obtain responses from the respondents on the relationship advertisement of job vacancies and service delivery in the selected ministries and departments in Anambra State from 2013 to 2024. The instrument was based on the objective and research question of the study while the respondents were required to indicate their level of agreement on a 5-point likert scale by indicating whether they agree with each of the questions contained in the questionnaire or otherwise by simply ticking (√) Strongly Agreed (SA) = 5, Agreed (A) = 4, Don't Know (DK) = 3, Disagreed (D) = 2 and Strongly Disagreed (SD) = 1, as appropriate.

3.6 Distribution of Questionnaire

The researchers used a face-to-face method for data collection by visiting the selected ministries and non-ministerial departments to physically administer the 343 copies of the questionnaire with the help of an assistant employed to abridge the time in the distribution and retrieval of the copies of the questionnaire. The assistant was acquainted with the essence of the study, the objectives, items contained in the questionnaire and how best to relate with the respondents for a successful outcome. In order to ensure maximum cooperation of the respondents, the distribution was scheduled to take place within three weeks in order to accommodate some staff who were off duty. The researcher and his assistant extracted an agreement that the questionnaire copies would be collected from each of the respondents in about 30 minutes after the distribution. Below is the table showing the distribution of the questionnaire.

Table 3.3: Distribution of Questionnaire

S/NO	MINISTRY/NON-MINISTERIAL DEPARTMENT	SAMPLE SIZE
€	Civil Service Commission	11
2	Office of Head of Service	36
3	Ministry of Finance	66
4	Ministry of Youth Development	27
5	Ministry of Information	10
6	Ministry of Health	39
7	Ministry of Agriculture	58
8	Ministry of Homeland Affairs	9
9	Ministry of Works	30
10	Ministry of Lands	46
11	Ministry of Budget and Economic Planning	11
Total		343
Percentage		100%

Source: Research Report 2025

3.7 Method of Data Analysis

The administered questionnaires were collated and scored in order to obtain the number of respondents that selected particular options listed on a 5-point Likert scale (Strongly Agree, Agree, Don't Know, Strongly Disagree and Disagree). The benchmark for establishing whether the respondents agreed or disagreed with each of the items on the questionnaire is 2.50. Mean and Standard Deviation was employed to answer the research question in line with the Resource-Based View Theory adopted in this study as framework of analysis. Test of hypotheses was carried out at 0.05 level of significance using Chi-Square (χ^2).

4.0 Data Presentation and Analysis

4.1 Return of Questionnaire

A total of 343 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the respondents. However, three hundred and twenty four (324) copies were returned. This represented 94% of the total number of distributed copies of the questionnaire while nineteen were not returned, representing 6% of the total distributed copies. Out of the returned copies, ten (10) copies were rejected as a result of improper completion by the respondents representing 3% of the total distributed and total returned copies. The remaining three hundred and fourteen (314) copies representing 91% of the total distributed and total return copies respectively formed the basis for the analysis. The return rate of the distributed questionnaire is presented on table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Return Rate of Distributed Questionnaire

Ministry/Non-Ministerial Department	No. Distributed	No. Returned	No. Not Returned	No. Condemned	No. Used
Civil Service Commission	11	11	0	0	11
Office of Head of Service	36	34	2	0	34
Ministry of Finance	66	61	5	0	61
Ministry of Youth Development	27	23	4	1	22
Ministry of Information	10	10	0	1	9
Ministry of Health	39	37	2	0	37
Ministry of Agriculture	58	56	2	4	52
Ministry of Homeland Affairs	9	9	0	0	9
Ministry of Works	30	28	2	2	26
Ministry of Lands	46	45	1	2	43
Ministry of Budget and Economic Planning	11	10	1	0	10
Grand Total	343	324	19	10	314
Percentage %	100 %	94 %	6%	3%	91%

Source: Research Report, 2025

Research Question

How has advertisement of job vacancies resulted in effective service delivery in the selected ministries and departments in Anambra state from 2013 to 2024?

This research question examined how advertisement of job vacancies resulted in effective service delivery in the selected ministries and departments in Anambra state from 2013 to 2024.

Table 4.2: Advertisement of Job Vacancies and Effective Service Delivery in Selected Ministries and Departments in Anambra State from 2013 to 2024

Responses	Strongly Agree	Agree	Don't Know	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
All vacant positions in my ministry/department were not given wide publicity	172 55%	62 20%	17 5%	34 11%	29 9%	314 100%
Advertisement of every vacant position in my ministry/department was not compulsory	120 38%	67 21%	44 14%	28 9%	55 18%	314 100%
Advertisement of vacant positions in my ministry/department did not attract effective employees	156 50%	51 16%	25 8%	50 16%	32 10%	314 100%
Advertisement of all vacant positions in my ministry/department did not take place from 2013 to 2024	164 52%	53 17%	37 12%	28 9%	32 10%	314 100%
All stages of recruitment in my ministry/department from 2013 to 2024 was not conducted openly	156 50%	56 18%	28 9%	40 13%	34 11%	314 100%
Recruitment into my ministry/department from 2013 to 2024 did not encourage transparent service delivery	168 54%	55 18%	20 6%	43 14%	28 9%	314 100%

Source: Research Report, 2025.

Table 4.2 reveals how lack of advertisement of job vacancies did not result in effective service delivery in selected ministries and departments in Anambra state from 2013 to 2024. The table shows that 172 or 55% of the respondents used indicated strongly agree that all vacant positions in their ministries/departments were not given wide publicity, 62 or 20% respondents indicated agree, 17 or 5% respondents indicated don't know, 34 or 11% respondents indicated disagree, and 29 or 9% respondents indicated strongly disagree.

Also, 120 or 38% of the respondents indicated strongly agree on the fact that advertisement of every vacant position in their ministries/departments was not compulsory, 67 or 21% respondents indicated agree, 44 or 14% respondents said don't know, 28 or 9% respondents indicated disagree, while 50 or 18% respondents indicated strongly disagree.

Similarly, 156 or 50% of the respondents indicated strongly agree that advertisement of vacant positions in their ministries/departments did not attract effective employees, 51 or 16% respondents indicated agree, 25 or 8% of the respondents indicated don't know, 50 or 16% respondents indicated disagree, and 32 or 10% respondents indicated strongly disagree.

On advertisement of all vacant position in my ministry/department did not take place from 2013-2024, 164 or 52% of the respondents indicated strongly agree, 53 or 17% respondents indicated agree, 37 or 12% respondents indicated don't know, 28 or 9% respondents indicated disagree, while 32 or 10% respondents indicated strongly disagree.

Again, 156 or 50% of the respondents indicated strongly agree on all stages of recruitment in their ministries/departments from 2013 to 2024 was not conducted openly, 56 or 18% respondents indicated agree, 28 or 9% respondents indicated don't know, and 40 or 13% respondents indicated disagree, while 34 or 11% respondents indicated strongly disagree.

As regards recruitment into my ministry/department did not encourage transparent service delivery, 168 or 54% of the respondents indicated strongly agree, 55 or 18% respondents indicated agree, 20 or 6% respondents indicated don't know, 43 or 14% respondents indicated disagree, while 28 or 9% respondents indicated strongly agree.

The pattern of responses presented and analyzed above shows that the fact that all vacant positions in the selected ministries and departments were not given wide publicity, was not compulsory, did not attract effective employees and consequently did not take place from 2013 to 2024, as well as the fact that all stages of recruitment from 2013 to 2024 was not conducted openly were part of the factors that did not result in effective service delivery in the selected ministries/departments from 2013 to 2024.

4.3 Test of Hypothesis

Hypothesis

Objective: Hypothesis one seeks to ascertain that advertisement of job vacancies has not resulted in effective service delivery in the selected ministries and departments in Anambra state from 2013 to 2024.

Statement of Hypothesis One

Advertisement of job vacancies has not resulted in effective service delivery in selected ministries and departments in Anambra state from 2013 to 2024.

Decision Criteria

When the computed value of chi-square (χ^2) is greater than ($>$) the table value of chi-square (X^2), the first hypothesis will be accepted.

Table 4.5: Decision

Ministry/Non-Ministerial Department	Strongly Agree	Agree	Don't Know	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
Civil Service Commission	7	4	2	3	1	17
Office of Head of Service	12	8	6	8	5	39
Ministry of Finance	16	12	5	10	4	47
Ministry of Youth Development	11	7	4	2	3	27
Ministry of Information	6	3	3	2	3	17
Ministry of Health	14	10	2	1	6	33
Ministry of Agriculture	26	15	6	9	7	63
Ministry of Homeland Affairs	3	2	2	1	2	10
Ministry of Works	12	3	2	2	1	20
Ministry of Lands	8	5	5	6	4	28
Ministry of Budget and Economic Planning	3	2	3	2	3	13
Total	118	71	40	46	39	314

Source: Research Report, 2025

Table 4.1.1: Observed Frequency for Hypothesis One

Calculation of Degree of Freedom (DF)

$$DF = (R - 1) (C - 1)$$

Where R = number of rows in the contingency table

C = number of columns in the contingency table

$$DF = (3 - 1) (5 - 1)$$

$$= 2 \times 4$$

$$= 8$$

At 0.05 significant level and 8 degrees of freedom, the total value of chi-square(x^2) =15.51

Computation of chi-square(x^2)

$$X^2 = \sum \frac{(o - e)^2}{e}$$

Where o = observed frequency

E = expected frequency

Expected frequency (e) is given by $\frac{RT \times CT}{GT}$

GT

Where RT = row total

CT = Column Total

GT = Grand Total

Table 4.6: Computation of Chi-Square (x^2) for Hypothesis One

Observed frequency (o)	Expected frequency (e)	(o - e)	(o - e) ²	$\frac{(o - e)^2}{e}$
31	40.59	-9.59	91.9681	2.28
20	24.42	-4.42	19.5364	0.80
12	13.76	-1.76	-3.0976	0.23
26	15.82	10.18	103.6324	6.55
19	13.41	5.59	31.2481	2.33
38	33.45	11.60	134.56	5.10
19	20.12	5.62	31.5844	2.36
17	11.34	5.87	34.4569	3.10
6	13.04	-8.5	72.25	4.98
9	11.05	-6.78	45.9684	2.91
49	43.97	5.03	25.3009	0.58
32	26.46	5.54	30.6916	1.16
11	14.90	-3.90	15.2100	1.02
14	17.14	-3.14	9.8596	0.56
11	14.53	-3.53	12.4609	0.86

				$X^2 = \frac{\sum(o - e)^2}{e} = 34.82$
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Source: Research Report, 2025

Decision

Since the computed value of chi-square (X^2) of 34.82 is greater than ($>$) the table value of chi-square of 15.51, hypothesis one is accepted. The study therefore established that advertisement of job vacancies has not resulted in effective service delivery in the selected ministries and departments in Anambra state from 2013 to 2024.

4.4. Discussion of Findings

The objective of the study was to examine how advertisement of job vacancies resulted in effective service delivery in the selected ministries and departments in Anambra state from 2013 to 2024. From the analysis of the data, it was established that advertisement of job vacancies has not resulted in effective service delivery in the selected ministries and departments in Anambra state from 2013 to 2024. It was revealed that all vacant positions in the ministries and departments were not given wide publicity. In fact, it was revealed that advertisement of every vacant position in the ministries and departments was not compulsory and did not attract effective employees. Apart from 2013, it did not take place subsequently. All stages of recruitment in the ministries and departments within the period were not, as well, conducted openly. These factors did not result in effective service delivery in the selected ministries and departments in Anambra state from 2013 to 2024.

5.0 Conclusion

The public sector is crucial for the implementation of government policies and programmes which are accomplished through competent employees recruited by way of open recruitment process. However, the sector seems to have remained inefficient as a result of perceived non-methodical recruitment process, particularly secret recruitments, adopted over time that could not result in effective service delivery. The perceived ineffective service delivery has, consequently, become worrisome and often linked to this practice of secret recruitments. It is on the basis of these concerns that this study was conceived to examine the relationship between advertisement of job vacancies and service delivery in selected ministries and departments in Anambra State from 2013 to 2024, more so as scanty scholarly literature has interrogated this concern.

The objective of the study was to examine how advertisement of job vacancies resulted in effective service delivery in the selected ministries and departments in Anambra state from 2013 to 2024. From the analysis of the data, it was established that advertisement of job vacancies has not resulted in effective service delivery in the selected ministries and departments in Anambra state within the period. It was revealed that all vacant positions in the ministries and departments were not given wide publicity. In fact, it was revealed that advertisement of every vacant position in the ministries and departments was not compulsory and did not attract effective employees. Apart from 2013, it did not take place subsequently. All stages of recruitment in the ministries and departments within the period were not, as well, conducted openly. These factors did not result in effective service delivery in the selected ministries and departments in Anambra state from 2013 to 2024.

6.0 Recommendations

Findings by the study necessitated the need to prioritize advertisement of job vacancies in Anambra state public sector, particularly in its civil service. All vacant positions in the state

civil service at every given time should be given wide publicity with objectives clearly made known in order to attract competent employees and by extension entrench the culture of transparency in the service and enhance its effectiveness. There is also the need for all stages of recruitment into the state civil service to be conducted openly. The state can leverage on her print, broadcast and official social media platforms to effectively disseminate information about job vacancies and their requirements with regards to the state civil service. In order to achieve better result, the state government may consider working through the State House of Assembly to criminalize secret recruitments into the service by way of appropriate legislation making it an offence punishable with strict penalties for employment to be carried out into the state civil service without evidence of repeated announcement of the vacancies for a specified reasonable period, not later than three weeks to the commencement of other processes of recruitment. The legislation should equally make it mandatory for all stages of the recruitment process to be conducted transparently and for the relevant authorities to mandatorily respond to any freedom of information request concerning how employment into the state civil service is conducted henceforth.

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